

ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENT, EMPLOYEE RETENTION, JOB SATISFACTION, AND PERFORMANCE AMONG PRIVATE SCHOOL TEACHERS: A STRUCTURAL MODEL

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Organizational Commitment, Employee Retention, Job Satisfaction, and Performance among Private School Teachers: A Structural Model

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Abstract

Teachers play an essential part in molding and imparting knowledge to the young minds of the students. The more teachers feel valued in their school, the more productive they are. Retaining and satisfying dedicated teachers becomes important. This study developed a structural model of teachers' commitment, retention, and satisfaction with performance. Four hundred twenty-two (422) secondary private school teachers participated in the study. Descriptive correlational and causal-comparative research designs were employed. Valid and reliable survey questionnaires were used as data collection tools. Structural Equation Model (SEM) was developed using AMOS. Results revealed that secondary private school teachers have a high level of commitment. Teachers are highly satisfied with advancement, recognition, working conditions, and interpersonal relationships. Teachers are just moderately satisfied with their salaries. There is a significant relationship between performance and organizational commitment, employee retention, and job satisfaction, and is also positive. The best predictors of teachers' performance are affective commitment, interpersonal relationships, working conditions, advancement and normative commitment, and intent to stay. All these predictors have a positive and direct impact on teachers' performance. The best model fit that explains teachers' job performance is Structural Model 5, anchored on organizational commitment, employee retention, and job satisfaction. Thus, the researcher recommends that DepEd should ensure that private schools maintain high standards and that teachers adequately be trained. Collaboration, reflection, and feedback help teachers improve their teaching skills and personal growth. School administrators and school principals can design programs and activities centered on improving the commitment, retention, and satisfaction of the teachers. Also, teachers might explore the importance of commitment in their schools.

Keywords: *affective commitment, perceived organizational support, interpersonal relationships, intent to stay, productivity, structural equation modeling*

Introduction

Teachers are essential in molding and imparting knowledge to students' young minds. Indeed, competitive students also need a competitive teacher. Teachers also serve as the backbone of schools, enabling them to create an environment conducive to academic growth and excellence. The more teachers feel valued in their school, the more productive they will become. Moreover, retaining and satisfying dedicated teachers becomes important as the demand for quality education rises.

Employee productivity results from employees' satisfaction (Muketha, 2017). However, this is not always the case for private school teachers. One of the biggest problems private schools face is a high employee turnover, which greatly affects the teachers' performance. Nowadays, most teachers want stability in their lives, want to provide food for their families, and want to improve their social status. According to a news article on Philstar.com, "A recent study conducted by a teachers' association found that most private school teachers in 2023 made less money than their counterparts in public schools and did not have a collective bargaining agreement with their companies. According to the group's analysis of the poll, "School size does not matter much in the setting of the school's starting salary for teachers, as P10,000 to P12,500 and P12,500 to P15,000 monthly salaries are the most common starting salary rates for private school teachers." (Chi, 2023).

However, because of the limited jobs offered in the Philippines, most fresh graduate teachers initially land jobs in private rather than public schools. Aside from this, poor working environment, ineffective management, little opportunity for promotion, lack of growth, and dissatisfaction lead to poor performance and unproductivity. Therefore, the school needs competent and productive employees to provide high-quality education and support to students.

In Abidogun's view (2023), teachers' motivation has been a major problem because of their duty to impart knowledge and skills to students. However, it has been determined that certified teachers can influence students' academic success and are typically more productive.

According to Khan (2015), "Organizational commitment is a powerful tool that can be used to achieve higher levels of performance and to develop and maintain discipline in an organization. The construct has been linked to various important outcome variables, including performance, absenteeism, employee turnover, tardiness, etc. Lack of commitment to the work and the organization can contribute to major problems that organizations face, such as high production costs and poor service". Teachers are regarded as nation-builders because the strength of every profession in every country stems from the knowledge and skills that teachers help to instill in their students (Duncan, 2016).

In addition, Singh (2019) said that employee retention mainly refers to the different steps firms take to motivate employees to stay with them longer. Keeping its talented personnel from departing is the primary basis for employee retention. Consequently, job satisfaction and employee retention are major determinants of every company's performance and longevity. Companies will be better positioned to prosper in today's highly competitive business environment, which particularly demands quality and cost efficiency if they create workplaces that attract, inspire, and retain skilled individuals (Irahor and Okolie, 2019).

Arif et. al (2019) noted that job satisfaction is defined as "a positive emotional state coming from the evaluation of one's job or work experiences." A person with high job satisfaction appears to have generally good views, while a person who is dissatisfied with their employment is more likely to have negative attitudes. Since job satisfaction is linked to reduced effort, acceptance of the current policies, the highest possible compensation, flexible work schedules, and good service delivery—all of which are seen as important parts of organizational success—it can be of great importance to a company (Eria, 2022).

Teachers' contribution to achieving educational goals and objectives is defined as job performance (Limon & Nartgun, 2020). According to Obilade (1999, as stated in Amin and Atta, 2013), teacher job performance can be defined as "The duties performed by a teacher at a School," during a particular period in the school system to achieve organizational goals.

On the other hand, productivity measures an organization's or an individual's efficiency in achieving goals. Productivity measures the growth rate in the respective organizations' capabilities to accomplish and fulfill their mission/goals and ensure that the quality of goods and services meets the expected standard (Ayeni & Akinola, 2020). For teachers to plan, carry out, and oversee every educational activity to meet school goals, productivity at work is the most important organizational aspect (Utami & Vioreza, 2021).

This paper delved into organizational commitment, employee retention, job satisfaction, and performance among private school teachers, with a detailed structural model to help comprehend the interrelationships between these critical aspects.

Research Objectives

The study specifically sought to:

1. Assess the level of secondary private school teachers' organizational commitment in terms of the following dimensions:
 - 1.1. affective commitment;
 - 1.2. normative commitment; and
 - 1.3. continuance commitment.
2. Evaluate the level of employee retention in terms of the following dimensions:
 - 2.1. perceived organizational support; and
 - 2.2. intent to stay.
3. Describe the level of job satisfaction in terms of the following dimensions:
 - 3.1. advancement;
 - 3.2. recognition;
 - 3.3. salary;
 - 3.4. working conditions; and
 - 3.5. interpersonal relationships.
4. Measure the level of performance in terms of productivity.
5. Correlate participants' performance with:
 - 5.1. organizational commitment;
 - 5.2. employee retention; and
 - 5.3. job satisfaction.
6. Identify which variables predict performance among teachers.
7. Develop a structural model that best fits the performance of teachers.

Methodology

Research Design

The study employed a descriptive-correlational and causal-comparative research design. This would aim to describe and establish relationships among variables. As mentioned by McCombes (2023), the goal of descriptive research was to accurately and systematically describe a population, circumstance, or phenomenon. Likewise, the study was correlational because part of the objectives of the study was to determine the relationship between the independent and dependent variables. As explained by Bhandari (2023), correlational research design looks into relationships between variables without the researcher controlling or manipulating any of them.

Respondents

The study consisted of a total of 422 secondary private school teachers of Lanao del Norte and Lanao del Sur for the school year 2024-2025. Excluded from the study were those teachers who did not give their consent, who were newly hired, on indefinite leave, study leave, school principals, and staff. The study used proportional stratified random sampling, which involves selecting random samples

from stratified groups in proportion to the population. This allowed researchers to produce a sample population that best represented the whole population being researched (Hayes, 2023). The margin of error is 5%.

Instrument

The research instrument for data gathering was a survey questionnaire composed of four parts. The four (4) sets of self-made questionnaires used in this study were all reliable. The Organizational Commitment Questionnaire is used to measure the level of organizational commitment among teachers, the Employee Retention Questionnaire to determine the teacher's level of perceived organizational support and intent to stay, Job Satisfaction Questionnaire to measure the level of job satisfaction among teachers, and Teacher's Performance Questionnaire that measures the performance through productivity of the teachers.

The questionnaires were reviewed by different experts. Based on the results of the content validation of the experts, the research instrument was pilot-tested to a sample of 30 private school teachers through Google Forms who were not part of the study. Individual reliability coefficients of items on the instruments were observed using the allowable range of 0.7–0.99. Items with coefficients less than 0.30 in the item total correlation were excluded. The total number of items that remain valid and reliable was used as the instrument's final items in the survey.

Procedure

First, the researcher requested permission from the dean of Liceo de Cagayan University's School of Business, Management, and Accountancy to conduct the study. Second, another letter was addressed to the Superintendent of the Schools Division of the Department of Education-Lanao del Norte and Lanao del Sur. Third, the researcher carried out the study protocol at the Office of the Ethics Review Board. Fourth, the researcher gave the SDS-approved letter to the private high school principals. Fifth, the researcher personally gave and collected survey questionnaires from teacher participants. Sixth, the completed questionnaires were counted using Microsoft Excel. Finally, the data was sent to the statistician for SPSS computation, analysis, and interpretation of the findings. Moreover, all information collected during the study was kept strictly confidential. All their responses were anonymized, and no personally identifiable information was associated with their answers.

The study included private school teachers who were currently working in the field and thus, willing to answer the research instrument. The participants' participation in this study was entirely voluntary, and they were informed of their rights in case they changed their decision not to participate. If it turns out that participants withdraw their participation, no risks and circumstances will be imposed on them. The participants were given 15 to 20 minutes to complete the survey questionnaires, after which they must return it to the researcher.

After the encoded tally, the data collected was stored in a safe file. Only the researcher had access to the said data with strict confidentiality. It would be upheld while the identity of the participants was unknown to anyone. Hence, the results of the research were only used for scholarly and instructional purposes.

The researcher revealed no potential conflicts of interest in connection with the research, writing, and/or publication of this study. Furthermore, there was no monetary compensation for participation in the study, and all volunteers were chosen voluntarily and freely. Rest assured that there were no risks involved with participating in this study. It won't also have any bearing whatsoever on how they would perform at work. The research would help bridge the knowledge gap in the literature about investigating these factors, especially concerning the satisfaction and performance of teachers. Closing the gap could lead to private-school teacher effectiveness and would focus on teacher well-being.

Data Analysis

For problems 1 to 4, descriptive statistics such as mean, and standard deviation were used to describe the variables in this study. For problem 5, Pearson product-moment correlation was utilized to determine the statistical significance of the relationship between teachers' performance and their organizational commitment, employee retention, and job satisfaction. For problem 6, Multiple Regression was employed to identify which variables, singly or in combination, best influence performance. For Problem 7, the researcher employed the Structural Equation Modelling to find the best-fit model for performance in terms of productivity among teachers.

Results and Discussion

The Level of Teachers' Organizational Commitment

Table 1. *Summary of the Level of Teachers' Organizational Commitment*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Affective Commitment	4.31	.727	High Level of Commitment
Normative Commitment	3.91	.704	High Level of Commitment
Continuance Commitment	3.13	.812	Moderate Level of Commitment
Overall Mean	3.78	.629	High Level of Commitment

The first statement of the problem investigated the level of teachers' organizational commitment. Table 1 shows that among the three involved indicators of teachers' organizational commitment, the affective commitment obtained the highest mean of 4.31 with a standard deviation of .727 indicating a high level of commitment. Meanwhile, normative commitment has an average mean of 3.91 and a standard deviation of 7.04 which also indicates a high level of commitment. However, continuance commitment has the lowest mean of 3.13 indicating a moderate level of commitment. Moreover, the overall mean of teachers' organizational commitment gained 3.78 with a standard deviation of .629 depicting a high level of commitment.

The results imply that teachers' organizational commitment indicates that their attachment to the school is largely driven by emotional and moral factors, as reflected by affective and normative commitment. Teachers are emotionally invested in the success of the school and feel a strong sense of obligation to remain part of the institution. However, for continuance commitment, their decision to stay is not significantly influenced by a perceived lack of alternatives or external constraints. Thus, a generally high level of organizational commitment, particularly influenced by teachers' emotional connection and sense of duty, could have positive implications for long-term teacher retention and overall performance. However, strengthening continuance commitment through enhanced professional development or career advancement opportunities could further solidify their dedication. With an overall descriptive level of high organizational commitment for all three (3) constructs perceived by the secondary private school teachers in Lanao del Norte and Lanao del Sur, according to Lagrimas (2024), teachers generally exhibit high levels of commitment, but this can vary based on specific conditions and contexts. Teachers' organizational commitment is significantly related to their hierarchical needs and perceived work opportunities. Those who feel secure in their employment and have access to professional development are more likely to demonstrate higher commitment levels (Bantilan et al., 2024).

The Level of Teacher Retention

Table 2. Summary of the Level of Teacher Employee Retention

Indicators	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Perceived Organizational Support	3.63	.814	High Level of Retention
Intent to Stay	3.16	.929	Moderate Level of Retention
Overall Mean	3.40	.810	High Level of Retention

The second problem statement focused on assessing the level of teachers' employee retention in terms of perceived organizational support and intent to stay. Among the indicators of teachers' employee retention, the perceived organizational support obtained the highest mean of 3.63 with a standard deviation of .814 indicating a high level of retention. However, the teachers' intent to stay has an average mean of 3.16 and a standard deviation of .929 which indicates a moderate level of retention. Moreover, the overall mean of teachers' employee retention gained 3.40 with a standard deviation of .810 depicting a high level of retention.

The results suggest that teachers' employee retention is strongly influenced by perceived organizational support demonstrating that when teachers feel supported by their institution, their likelihood of remaining increases. However, despite this support, some teachers may still be uncertain about long-term retention, possibly due to external factors such as better career opportunities or personal motivations. While organizational support is effective in fostering retention, additional strategies may be necessary to strengthen teachers' intent to stay, such as competitive benefits and career development opportunities.

The Level of Employees' Job Satisfaction

Table 3. Summary of the Level of Teacher Job Satisfaction

Indicators	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Advancement	3.78	.792	Highly Satisfied
Recognition	3.66	.774	Highly Satisfied
Salary	3.27	1.174	Moderately Satisfied
Working Conditions	3.68	.766	Highly Satisfied
Interpersonal Relationships	4.02	.713	Highly Satisfied
Overall Mean	3.68	.629	Highly Satisfied

The third statement of the problem measured the level of job satisfaction among private school teachers. The table indicates the level of teacher job satisfaction in terms of advancement, recognition, salary, working conditions, and interpersonal relationships. Among the indicators of teachers' job satisfaction, interpersonal relationships obtained the highest mean of 4.02 with a standard deviation of .713 indicating a high level of satisfaction.

However, the salary has an average mean of 3.27 and a standard deviation of 1.174 which indicates a moderate level of satisfaction. Moreover, the overall mean of teachers' job satisfaction gained 3.68 with a standard deviation of .629 depicting a high level of satisfaction.

The data implies that while teachers are generally satisfied with their jobs, particularly in terms of interpersonal relationships, there is still an area of concern regarding salary. Job satisfaction in terms of interpersonal relationships suggests that strong connections with colleagues and a supportive work environment are key contributors to job satisfaction. The data also suggests that teachers are largely content with their work environment, though addressing salary concerns could further enhance their overall satisfaction.

The Level of Performance in terms of Productivity

Table 4. *Mean and Standard Deviation of Performance of Private School Teachers in Terms of Productivity*

Indicators	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Productivity	4.20	0.687	Very Good

The fourth statement of the problem investigated the level of private school teachers' performance in terms of productivity. Table 16 illustrates the job satisfaction of private school teachers in terms of productivity which features fifteen significant items with their respective mean, standard deviation, description, and interpretation. The data shows that the statements, "I collaborate with colleagues to share successful teaching strategies and resources", and "I reflect on student performance data to inform instructional decision-making and identify areas for growth" gained the highest mean of 4.26 which shows agreement among respondents and is interpreted as very good. Meanwhile, the statement, "I ask mentors or colleagues for feedback to pinpoint areas where my teaching methods need to be improved" gained the lowest mean of 3.99 showing agreement and interpreted as very good. Thus, the overall mean of 4.20 with a standard deviation of .687 shows agreement indicating very good.

The data implies that private school teachers exhibit a very good level of performance concerning productivity. The results reflecting collaboration with colleagues and reflective use of student performance data, highlight the teachers' active engagement in enhancing instructional strategies and personal growth. Seeking feedback for improving teaching methods reinforces a consistent trend of satisfaction and productivity among respondents.

The Relationship Between Job Performance and the following Independent Variables: Organizational Commitment, Employee Retention, And Job Satisfaction

Table 5. *Correlation Analysis Between Performance and Organizational Commitment, Employee Retention, and Job Satisfaction among Private School Teachers*

Variables	Correlation Coefficient	P-Value	Interpretation
Organizational Commitment	.655**	.000	Significant
Affective Commitment	.674**	.000	Significant
Normative Commitment	.634**	.000	Significant
Continuance Commitment	.369**	.000	Significant
Employee Retention	.563**	.000	Significant
Perceived Organizational Support	.585**	.000	Significant
Intent to Stay	.470**	.000	Significant
Job Satisfaction	.706**	.000	Significant
Advancement	.648**	.000	Significant
Recognition	.590**	.000	Significant
Salary	.535**	.000	Significant
Working Conditions	.655**	.000	Significant
Interpersonal Relationships	.672**	.000	Significant

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

The fifth problem of this study presents the correlation analysis between performance and organizational commitment, employee retention, and job satisfaction among private school teachers. The results show strong, positive correlations between job satisfaction, organizational commitment, employee retention, with job performance, as indicated by significant correlation coefficients at the 0.01 level. Specifically, job satisfaction (.706) and affective commitment (.674) demonstrate the highest correlations, suggesting that teachers who are more satisfied with their jobs and emotionally committed to their organizations tend to exhibit better performance. Additionally, factors like working conditions (.655), interpersonal relationships (.672), and recognition (.590) are also strongly associated with performance. Continuance commitment, although still significant, exhibits a lower correlation (.369), suggesting that the obligation to remain in the organization has a smaller relationship with performance. This association was statistically established using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient, or Pearson r.

The Variables that Predict Job Performance among Teachers

The sixth problem of this study presents the variables that significantly influence teachers' performance. The table features the unstandardized and standardized coefficients with statistical interpretation. The table presents a multiple regression analysis between job performance (productivity) and various factors of organizational commitment, employee retention, and job satisfaction among private school teachers. The model shows a strong relationship, with an R² value of .631, meaning that 63.1% of the variance in performance is explained by the factors included in the model. Affective commitment (organizational commitment) ($\beta = .322$), which surfaced as the best predictor to positively impact the performance of teachers. Not too far behind is the interpersonal relationship (job satisfaction) ($\beta = .296$), which positively influences teachers' performance. Additionally, working conditions ($\beta = .186$), advancement

($\beta = .128$), and intent to stay ($\beta = .133$) are significant predictors of job performance, as indicated by their high beta values and significant p-values.

Table 6. The Variables that Best Predict Teacher's Job Performance

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standard Coefficients	t-value	Sig
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	.590	.141		4.200	.000
Affective Commitment	.304	.046	.322	6.619	.000
Normative Commitment	.111	.052	.114	2.147	.032
Interpersonal Relationship	.285	.043	.296	6.596	.000
Working Conditions	.167	.050	.186	3.351	.001
Advancement	.111	.043	.128	2.558	.011
Intent to Stay	-.099	.034	-.133	-2.914	.004

R= .794f R2= .631 R2 Adjusted= .625 F value= 118.124 p-value= .000g

The Structural Model Best Fits the Performance of Teachers

The last problem that his research endeavored to answer was to explore various structural models and identify which best fits teachers' performance. This problem can be effectively addressed using structural equation modeling. Structural equation modeling generates a model that hypothesizes correlations among latent and observable variables, both directional and non-directional (SEM).

Figure 1 or Structural Model 5 for Teacher Job Performance (PERFORM), presents three latent variables, namely, Organizational Commitment (ORGCO), Employee Retention (EMPRE), and Job Satisfaction (JOBSA). Moreover, they were co-varied in this model and were presumed to predict Performance (PERFORM). As a latent variable, Organizational Commitment (ORGCO) was measured with constructs, namely Affective Commitment (AFFE_OC) and Normative Commitment (NORM_OC). These were the two dependent variables for Organizational Commitment (ORGCO) and error terms. On the other hand, Employee Retention (EMPRE) was measured with three measured variables, which are Perceived Organizational Support (POS_ER) and Intent to Stay (ITS_ER). These two are the dependent variables for Employee Retention (EMPRE) and error terms. Alternatively, Job Satisfaction (JOBSA) is measured with three variables, which are Advancement (ADVA_JS), Recognition (RECO_JS), and Working Conditions (WOCO_JS). These three are the dependent variables for Job Satisfaction (JOBSA).

Figure 1. Structural Model 5 on Teachers' Performance

Legend:

- PROD_PF – Productivity
- AFFE_OC – Affective Commitment
- NORM_OC – Normative Commitment
- CONT_OC – Continuance Commitment
- POS_ER – Perceived Organizational Support
- ITS_ER – Intent to Stay
- ADVA_JS – Advancement
- RECO_JS – Recognition
- SALA_JS – Salary
- WOCO_JS – Working Conditions
- INRE_JS – Interpersonal Relationship

Table 7 presents the Standard Regression Analysis of Weights and Beta Coefficients of Structural Model 5 for Performance (PERFORM). As presented in the table below, Organizational Commitment (ORGCA) ($p > .05$), Employee Retention (EMPRES) ($p > .05$), and Job Satisfaction (JOBSA) ($p > .05$) have no significant effect on Teachers' Performance (PERFORM). This means that even if teachers are not committed, retained, and satisfied, they are still likely to perform very well in their teaching careers.

Organizational Commitment (ORGCA) has the highest significant effect on Normative Commitment (NORM_OC) (.903) ($p < .05$). However, it has no significant effect on Affective Commitment (AFFE_OC) ($p > .05$). Additionally, Employee Retention (EMPRES) has a significant effect on Perceived Organizational Support (POS_ER) (.667) ($p < .05$). But, it has no effect on Intent to Stay (ITS_ER) ($p > .05$). Moreover, Job Satisfaction (JOBSA) has a significant effect on Working Conditions (WOCO_JS) (.897) and Recognition (RECO_JS) (.847). It has no significant effect on Advancement (ADVA_JS) ($p > .05$). Finally, Performance (PERFORM) has no direct effect on Productivity (PROD_PF) ($p > .05$).

Table 7. Standardized Regression Weights of Structural Model 5

Variables	Beta	S.E.	C.R.	Beta	P-value
PERFORM <--- ORGCO	1.062			.392	
PERFORM <--- EMPRES	.662			.214	
PERFORM <--- JOBSA	.546			.236	
PROD_PF <--- PERFORM	.376			.926	
AFFE_OC <--- ORGCO	1.000			.879	
ITS_ER <--- EMPRES	1.000			.599	
POS_ER <--- EMPRES	1.018	.046	22.021	.667	***
ADVA_JS <--- JOBSA	1.000			.894	
RECO_JS <--- JOBSA	.878	.034	25.510	.847	***
NORM_OC <--- ORGCO	1.000	.051	19.531	.903	***
WOCO_JS <--- JOBSA	.951	.034	27.980	.897	***

Table 8 presents the Standard Indices of Fit Measures of Structural Model 5 for teachers' teaching competencies. As shown in the table, the Model 5 fit value for CMIN/DF is 1.353, less than 2.0; p-value is .074, greater than .05; GFI is .963, greater than .95; NFI is .962, greater than .95; TLI is .961, greater than .95; CFI is .977, greater than .95; and RMSEA is .027, greater than .05, which all satisfy the standard value. This implies that Structural Model 5 is the best Fit Model for teachers' performance.

Table 8. Standard of Fit Indices in Structural Model 5

Standard Indicators	Standard Value	Model Fit Value
CMIN/DF	< 2.00	1.353
P-value	> 0.05	.074
GFI	> 0.95	.963
NFI	> 0.95	.962
TLI	> 0.95	.961
CFI	> 0.95	.977
RMSEA	< 0.05	.027

Legend: CMIN/DF – Chi-Square Minimum/ Degrees of Freedom, CFI – Comparative Fit Index, RMSEA – Root Mean Square Error of Approximation, NFI – Normed Fit Index, TLI – Tucker-Lewis Index, GFI – Goodness of Fit Index

In general, RMSEA values less than 0.05 indicate an excellent fit, whereas values above 0.08 imply an adequate fit (Li & Hau, 2012). Therefore, model 5 successfully met the standard values for all the seven index criteria. This model is the ideal choice for teachers' job performance as it fulfills all seven criteria for the best-fit model. Model 5 is the best choice because it corresponds to the observed data and the model's predicted value. According to the Performance model, organizational commitment, employee retention, and job satisfaction all have a positive and direct impact on teachers' performance.

Conclusions

Based on the study's findings, the following conclusions are drawn:

The organizational commitment of secondary private school teachers is high. Teachers are emotionally invested in the success of the school and feel a strong obligation to remain part of the institution. However, their decision to stay is not significantly influenced by alternatives or external constraints. Perceived organizational support is strongly influenced by teachers' retention, but they may still be uncertain about long-term retention due to external factors. The study also measures teachers' job satisfaction, revealing high levels of satisfaction with advancement, recognition, working conditions, and interpersonal relationships. However, in terms of salary, they are just moderately satisfied. Teachers require a strong professional development plan and a balance between lighthearted and serious work-related activities. Satisfied teachers provide quality services efficiently and positively influence students' behavior and interest in learning and academic activities.

Teachers' productivity is high. Collaboration, reflection, and feedback enhance instructional strategies and personal growth. Teachers'

performance is crucial for student achievement, shaping minds, and employing diverse teaching methods. Holding students accountable for their learning leads to higher success rates. Therefore, teachers' performance is key to the educational system.

There are six best predictors of teachers' performance. The top predictor is affective commitment, followed by interpersonal relationships, working conditions, advancement and normative commitment, and intent to stay. All these predictors have a positive and direct impact on teachers' performance, which means that when these variables' levels increase, the teachers' performance also increases.

The best model fit that explains teachers' job performance is Structural Model 5, anchored on organizational commitment, employee retention, and job satisfaction. This is called Kernel Arnoco's Model of Private Secondary School Teachers' Performance.

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